

EPIDEMIOLOGICAL AND CAPROCULTURE STUDIES OF STRONGYLE INFECTION IN GOATS UNDER DIFFERENT FARM CONDITION AT JABALPUR.

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ABSTRACT

Parasitic diseases undoubtedly inflict enormous economic loss annually through morbidity and mortality in the livestock. Grazing ruminants are often exposed to multiple species of parasitic gastrointestinal nematodes (GIN), which cause gastroenteritis (Kassai, 1999). The present study was aimed to undergo the caproculture and epidemiological study of strongyle infection under different farm condition at Jabalpur. A total of 500 goats belonged to the organized and unorganized sector of Jabalpur were screened over a period of 15 months for the symptoms of impaired appetite, weight loss, severe anemia, persistent diarrhea. The overall prevalence of gastrointestinal Strongyles was 37.20%. Goats from unorganized sector had more prevalence (43.35%) of Strongyle infection. Female goats (43.01%) and goats between >1-2 years of age had showed more (54.13%) prevalence. Non-descript breed of goats showed higher (58.55%) prevalence of Strongyle infection. Maximum prevalence (55.36%) of Strongyle infection was observed during monsoon seasons. During caproculture investigation larvae of *Haemonchus* sp were more prevalent (64.05%) in Jabalpur.

Keywords: Goats, Strongyle, Caproculture

Introduction

In India livestock and agriculture are closely integrated in the predominantly agriculture-based national economy. Among all farm animals, goats have the widest ecological range and have been poor people's most reliable livelihood resource. Grazing ruminants are often exposed to multiple species of parasitic gastrointestinal nematodes (GIN), which cause gastroenteritis (Kassai, 1999)¹. Gastrointestinal nematodes targeting the abomasum, small and large intestines of sheep and goats include different species of *Haemonchus*, *Ostertagia*, *Teladorsagia*, *Trichostrongylus*, *Nematodirus*, *Oesophagostomum*, *Chabertia* and *Bunostomum* (Zajac, 2006). Parasitic diseases undoubtedly inflict enormous economic loss annually through morbidity and mortality in the livestock. Gastrointestinal (GI) parasitism directly or indirectly accentuates the economic losses through lowered fertility, compromised work capacity, suppressed food intake, weight gain and milk production, increased treatment cost and mortality in the heavily parasitized animals (Choubisa and Jaroli, 2013).

Materials and Methods

The work was conducted in the Department of Veterinary Medicine, College of Veterinary Science & A.H., Jabalpur, Livestock Farm, Amanala, Nanaji Deshmukh Veterinary Science University (NDVSU), Jabalpur Madhya Pradesh and different nearby villages of Jabalpur. The

study was conducted for a period of fifteen months from October 2021 to January 2022. For this study, a total numbers of 500 goats of organized and unorganized sectors were screened for the symptoms of impaired appetite, weight loss, severe anaemia and persistent diarrhea. Before collection of faecal samples, signalment (age, sex) of the animal was also recorded.

Collection of Samples

Faecal samples were collected in individually labelled polythene bags and taken to the laboratory at the earliest for further examination by standard faecal examination methods i.e., sugar flotation and sedimentation techniques. The faecal samples positive for strongyle infection in a month were, pooled area wise and culture in the laboratory by petridish method . A drop of preserved sediment containing larvae was placed on a glass slide, mixed with a drop of Lugol's iodine or aqueous Safranin and then examined under dry magnifications of the compound microscope after applying a cover slip over the preparation. 100 L₃ parasites were counted and identification of Strongyle larvae was done with the help of the key and plates provided by Ministry of Agriculture, Fishery and Food (1971).

Table 01: Sources of Animals Screened Under the Study

S.NO	Place	No of animals screened
1.	Amanala	227
2.	Adhartal	40
3.	Padariya	17
4.	Khamariya	32
5.	Pipariya	46
6.	Sonpur	20
7.	Sunderpur	58
8.	Saraswahi	50
9.	Rampur	10
	Total	500

Larvae Culture Methods and Recovery of Third-Stage Strongyle Larvae

To distinguish between the genus of strongyles, faeces containing strongyle eggs were allowed to incubate at room temperature for several days till the larvae hatch from the eggs. The newly hatched larvae can then be identified (Sloss *et al.*, 1994)

Petridish Method

A large lump of faeces was taken in a watch glass or small petridish. The faeces should be neither too hard nor too soft. This dish or watch glass was placed in another larger petridish having a small quantity of water. The larger petridish was covered with another dish or jar and was kept it in the

dark, at room temperature. The larvae migrate from the faecal lump after hatching out from the eggs. Many of the larvae had reached the infective stage by that time facilitating specific diagnosis. **Identification of Nematode (Strongyle) Larvae:** A drop of preserved sediment containing larvae was placed on a glass slide, mixed with a drop of Lugol's iodine or aqueous Safranin and then examined under dry magnification of the compound microscope, after applying a cover slip over the preparation. Identification of the strongyle larvae was done with the help of keys and plates provided by Ministry of Agriculture, Fishery and Food (1971).

Statistical Analysis of the Data

The association of different risk factors (i.e., season, age and sex) with the prevalence of parasites was tested employing Chi-square test of independence of attributes. Risk factor correlations with $P < 0.05$ were considered significant and $P < 0.01$ were considered highly significant (Snedecor and Cochran, 1994).

Results and Discussion

Overall Prevalence of Strongyles in Goats

An epidemiological survey was conducted to determine the prevalence of strongyles in goats, over a period of 15 months (October 2021 - January 2022) in and around Jabalpur, Madhya Pradesh. Of total 500 goats were included in this study, 186 goats were found strongyles positive in the institute's Amanala Goat Farm and periurban villages. Thus, overall prevalence of strongyles in goats in and around Jabalpur was 37.20 per cent (Table 02; Figure 01).

Table 02: Overall Prevalence of Gastrointestinal Strongyles in Goats in and Around Jabalpur

No. examined	No. positive for GI strongyle	Positive (%)
500	186	37.2

Figure 01: Over all prevalence of gastrointestinal strongyles in goats in and around Jabalpur

These findings are in agreement with Zivinorava *et al.* (2016), Das *et al.* (2017), and Anugrah *et al.* (2018) who recorded 31.0 per cent, 32.6 per cent and 38.3 per cent prevalence, respectively. However, higher prevalence of gastrointestinal nematodes was reported by Rupa and Portugaliza (2016), Kusumlata *et al.* (2018), Ghimire and Bhattarai (2019), Mohammedsalih *et al.* (2019), and Income *et al.* (2021) as 62.0, 61.4, 59.3, 82.0 and 86.3 per cent, respectively.

The variation in the result of prevalence of strongyle sp. in present study with earlier reports may be attributed to various factors including the selection of animals, season, managerial practices in different farms, preventive strategies, existence of unfavorable climatic and environmental factors (Andrews, 1999). Direct relationship exists between the magnitude of atmospheric moisture and prevalence of animal parasitosis (Regassa *et al.*, 2006), and desiccation inhibits the development and growth of parasites reducing infection (Dagnachew *et al.*, 2011).

Sector-Wise Prevalence

Prevalence of gastrointestinal parasites was recorded significantly higher ($P < 0.01$) in unorganized sector (43.35%) than under organized (31.84%). These findings are in close agreement with Pant *et al.* (2009) who reported higher prevalence in the small household goats (96.15%), compared to farm goats (90%). Singh *et al.* (2016), Kusumlata *et al.* (2018) surprisingly found higher prevalence in the farm goats, compared to field goats. The variation in the prevalence rate may be attributable to regular use of broad-spectrum anthelmintic drugs in the well-managed organized farms under veterinary supervision by the well-informed animal attendants with appropriate nutritional support and preventive measures. (Table 03; Figure 02).

Table 03: Sector Wise Prevalence of Gastrointestinal Strongyles in Goats in and Around Jabalpur

Sector	No. examined	No. positive for GI Strongyle
Organized	267	85 (31.84%)
Unorganized	233	101 (43.35%)
$X^2 = 2.54; p < 0.001$ (significant)		

Figure 02: Sector Wise Prevalence of Gastrointestinal Strongyles in Goats in and Around Jabalpur

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Age-Wise Prevalence

Age wise prevalence study had showed the prevalence rates of 61/152 (40.13%) in the 0-1 year, 72/133 (54.13%) in >1-2 years, 32/105 (30.48%) in >2-3 years, and 21/110 (19.09%) in over 3 years age groups goats, Analysis of data revealed significantly higher prevalence in the >1-2 years of age group, followed by animals in the age groups of 0-1 year and >2-3 years. The lowest values were recorded in the over 3 years of age group animals. (Table 04; Figure 03).

Table 04: Age Wise Prevalence of Gastrointestinal Strongyle in Goats in and Around Jabalpur

Age groups (years)	Goats examined (n=500)	No. positive for GI strongyles
0-1	152	61 (40.13%)
1-2	133	72 (54.13%)
2-3	105	32 (30.48%)
3	110	21 (19.09%)
$X^2 = 36.24 ; p < 0.05$ (Significant)		

Figure 03:Age-wise Prevalence of Gastrointestinal Strongyles in Goats in and Around Jabalpur

Similar findings are on record (Rupa and Portugaliza, 2016; Kusumlata *et al.*, 2017; Anugrah *et al.*, 2018 and Limbat *et al.*, 2022). Adult goats were more prone to strongyle burden, compared to the young ones. On the contrary, many other investigators (Urquhart *et al.*, 1996; Vlassoff *et al.*, 2001 and Khajuria *et al.*, 2012) reported that younger goats less than 1 year in age were more prone to infection, *cf.* the older ones. The enigmatic differences in the prevalence rate of strongylosis in goats (present and previous reports) are ascribable to gross variation in the geo-climatic conditions in different locations, and managerial protocols.. Similar findings are on record (Rupa and Portugaliza, 2016 ; Kusumlata *et al.*, 2018; Anugrah *et al.*, 2018 and Limbat *et al.*, 2022) . Adult goats were more prone to strongyle burden, compared to the young ones. On the contrary, many other investigators (Urquhart *et al.*, 1996 ; Vlassoff *et al.*, 2001 and Khajuria *et al.*, 2012) reported that younger goats less than 1 year in age were more prone to infection, *cf.* the older ones.

Gender-Wise Prevalence

Gender wise, the prevalence rates of 69/228 (30.26%) in males and 117/272 (43.01%) in females were recorded. Thus, the intensity of infection was significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher in females, compared to males. (Table 05; Figure 04).

Table 05: Gender-Wise Prevalence of Gastrointestinal Strongyles in Goats in and Around Jabalpur

Sex	No of sample examined	Number of samples positive
Male	228	69

		(30.26%)
Female	272	117 (43.01%)
X ² value= 3.99 df=1 p<0.05(significant)		

Figure 04: Gender-Wise Prevalence of Gastrointestinal Strongyle in Goats in and Around Jabalpur

Temporary loss of acquired immunity against gastrointestinal nematodes near the parturition time, physiological stress associated with parturition and lactation in female animals reduce the immune tolerance to infections (Blood and Radostists, 2000). Female gender predisposition observed in the present study is consistent with the published reports: 73.21% (Chavan *et al.*, 2008) and 53.67% (Kuchai *et al.*, 2011). However, Bhat *et al.* (2012) reported that male sheep have higher prevalence (75.6%) than the females.

Breed-Wise Prevalence

The breed-wise prevalence of gastrointestinal strongyles was studied. The specified infection rate 58.55% (89/152) was highest in non-descript breed, followed by Barbari 37.14% (39/105), Black Bengal 31.34% (21/67), Jamnapari 29.17% (14/48) and Sirohi 17.97% (23/128). (Table 06; Figure 05).

Table 06: Breed-Wise Prevalence of Gastrointestinal Strongyles in Goats in and Around Jabalpur.

Breed	No of sample examined	No of affected
Barbari	105	39 (37.14%)
Sirohi	128	23 (17.97%)
Black bengal	67	21 (31.34%)
Jamnapari	48	14 (29.17%)
Non descript	152	89 (58.55%)
$X^2 = 16.47 ; p < 0.05$ (Significant)		

Figure 5: Breed wise prevalence of gastrointestinal strongyle in goats in and around Jabalpur.

The data on gastrointestinal strongyles revealed significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher prevalence in non-descript breed (58.55%) compared to the established breeds of goats. These observations are in general agreement with reports of Dappawar *et al.* (2018)¹ who reported breed-wise prevalence to be 48.93% in non-descript breed and 52.89% in Osmanabadi breed of goats. The variation in the susceptibility to infection with a specified gastrointestinal parasite largely depends primarily on the genetic configuration of the breed and partly on the environment. Susceptibility to any infection also depends on the management practices, topography of the geographic area, drainage of waste water, hygiene and sanitation conditions favourable or otherwise for parasitic development. Thus, variation in the breed-wise prevalence rate of the endoparasite in a particular geographic area is mainly attributable to the genetic make-up of the host animal species.

Season-Wise Prevalence

The season-wise prevalence of gastrointestinal strongyles was studied. The data on gastrointestinal strongyles revealed significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher prevalence (55.36%) in monsoon season compared to the winter (30.49%) and summer seasons (20.93%). (Table 07; Figure 06).

Table 07: Season-Wise Prevalence of Gastrointestinal Strongyle in Goats in and Around Jabalpur

Seasons	No. of sample examined	No of sample positive
Winter	246	75 (30.49%)
Summer	86	18 (20.93%)
Monsoon	168	93 (55.36%)
$X^2 = 8.038$; $p < 0.05$ (Significant)		

Figure 6: Season Wise Prevalence Of Gastrointestinal Strongyles in Goats in and Around Jabalpur

These findings are in close agreement with the published reports (Bhat *et al.*, 2012 ; Khajuria *et al.*, 2012 ; Das *et al.*, 2017¹; Jas and Pandit, 2017 ; Syamala *et al.*, 2021). Climatic conditions and ambient moisture content also significantly modulate the rate of larval development and migration in the host tissues.

Caproccultural Studies

The overall composition of caproccultural larvae revealed highest prevalence of *Haemonchus sp.* (64.05%), followed in sequence by *Trichostrongylus sp.* (14.20%), *Oesophagostomum sp.* (10.15%), *Strongyloides sp.* (6.43%) and *Bunostomum sp.* (5.17%). This finding is consistent with the published reports (Singh *et al.*, 2016 , Das *et al.*, 2017 ; Kusumlata *et al.*, 2018). Agro-ecology and climatic conditions are claimed to play an important role in the development and survival of infective stages of strongyle nematodes in grazing pastures. (Table 08; Figure 07).

Table 08: Generic distribution of strongyles larvae in and around Jabalpur

Type of strongyle larvae (n=186)	Generic composition (%)
<i>Haemonchus</i> sp	64.05
<i>Trichostrongylus</i> sp.	14.20
<i>Oesophagostomum</i> sp.	10.15
<i>Strongyloides</i> sp.	6.43
<i>Bunostomum</i> sp.	5.17

Figure 7: Generic composition (%) of strongyles larvae in and around Jabalpur

Conclusion

The overall prevalence of strongyle infection was 37.20%. Goats from unorganized sector, female goats, goats of age group greater than 1-2 years of age, non-descript breed of goats and monsoon season had showed higher prevalence of strongyle infection. Moreover the prevalence of

Haemonchus spp was higher in and around Jabalpur. This data will help the veterinarians of the area in planning future research and control strategies.

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